

Statutory Bodies' Functions, Current Situation, Challenges and Opportunities in Management Education Systems in Indian Higher Education Institutions: Research Analysis

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Abstract: India is a centre for management education since it has several management schools and a rising need for qualified businesspeople. India's ability to compete in the global market depends on the Caliber of its management education. Approximately 3,000 part-time and close to 5,000 full-time MBAs are produced annually by Indian management schools. The Indira Gandhi Open University, the AIMA, and a few other universities offer distance learning programs that produce approximately 1,000 MBA-equivalent graduates. The most employable cohort in 2024 was those with an MBA (71.2% employability), followed by those with a B.E./B. Tech (64.7% employability). With 68.4% employability, IT engineers were the most employable engineering students in 2024, followed by computer science students with 66% employability. At the global level, job opportunities are avail to Management graduates who have shown their keen knowledge and interest at the global level. Based on the geopolitical opportunities also many challenges in multilevel fields to grow at the international level. From this research, the researchers confirm the growth of educational institutions and management education programs with various levels of accreditation facilities, standards, and qualities, providing good atmospheric conditions in digital environments with placement for all intakes. 119517 students are placed at a national level from 403202 intakes in 2021-22 is 13.06%.

Keywords: Management Course. Management education, current trends, Challenges, opportunities. Higher education institutions.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Over the past 70 years, management education in India has undergone significant change. There was significant demand for MBA education throughout the 1990s economic liberalization era and the ensuing rapid economic development. This made it possible for numerous public and private institutions to open offices and offer MBA programs across the nation. Due to the MBA becoming a popular (read: "glamorous") degree, it is generally thought to be the answer to any business problem. However, as the number of MBA programs has increased, their structural flaws have persisted, creating several problems. The current upheaval brought on by the epidemic and technological disruption has highlighted the shortcomings in our management education and the urgent need for corrective action to solve them. Due to the swift and significant changes affecting the different components of the business environment, management education in India is poised for a revolution. The industry is looking for managers with cutting-edge abilities and skills. This change is probably going

to completely change how management education is taught in the nation in terms of both design and substance.

2. HISTORY OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION:

In the modern world, management is essential to the administration of public projects, commercial enterprises, and service sectors to make the best use of the resources at hand. The word "management," which dates to the 16th and 17th centuries, is derived from the Latin "manus," the Italian "maneggiare," and the French "management" and "management." The word "management" implies authority over others, particularly physical labourers, to complete tasks and make decisions regarding the use of available resources.

Administration is the foundation everywhere, and management education is the backbone of the organisation. Globalisation is a chronological process of managerial activities and the culture of the arts and sciences, as well as the theory, practical skills, and knowledge of society as it observes the difficulties of the new economic revolution throughout the world. When it came to trade, capitalisation, and population immigration, the First World War, which lasted from 1870 to 1974, quickly supplanted the new political and economic policies of the time. This led to changes in communication, technology, and development, and it also became a major factor in globalisation, which streamlined management education worldwide.

The free market philosophy of education is the focus of globalisation. The *École Supérieure de Commerce* of Paris was established in 1819, and the University of Pennsylvania's Wharton School was established in 1881 as the first business school within a larger university. The history of management studies is only fifty years old.

The first college-level business school, Sydenham College, was established in Mumbai in 1913. The number of business schools has increased since 1990. The founding of management schools modelled after the MIT of America and the Harvard Institute in the United Kingdom was spearheaded by former Indian Prime Minister Pandit Jawahar Lal Nehru. The Institute of Management in Kolkata and Ahmedabad was founded in 1962 (2012)³.

The history of management education in India dates to the 19th century, when the British government dominated the country, and management education was centered on the commercial side of the company and aimed to meet their needs.

The southern city of Chennai (Madras) hosted the first "Pacchiappa Charities" business and commercial school in 1886. In keeping with Madras, the British government started secondary school-level commerce courses at the Presidency College in Calcutta in 1903. The courses covered a wide range of topics, particularly accounting, shorthand, typing, correspondence, managerial communication, and secretarial practice. In 1913, the College Level Management School—the first higher education institution for management—was founded in Mumbai, India. Later, in 1920, it was founded in Delhi as Commerce College and changed its name to Shri Rama College of Commerce later.

Since the 19th century when the British dominated India, management education was a rich tradition in that country, with a concentration on the economic side of the company and meeting the demands of the British government. The first "PacchiappaCharities" business and commercial school was established in Chennai, Madras, in 1886. Following Madras' example, the British government started secondary school-level commerce courses at Calcutta's Presidency College in 1903, covering a wide range of topics, particularly accounting, shorthand, typing, correspondence, managerial communication, and secretarial

practice. The College Level Management School, India's first higher education institution for management, was founded in Mumbai in 1913. then, in 1920, it was founded in Delhi as Commerce College and then changed its name to Shri Rama College of Commerce⁵.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

3.1. Balamurugan et al (2019)⁵: To overcome the obstacles faced by management schools, management education offers a range of opportunities through the provision of standardized, high-quality management education and international connections that enable students to become global talent effective managers, improve the quality of the educational system globally, and create jobs in multinational corporations (MNCs) and other places. Furthermore, liberalization, privatization, and globalization (LPG) give people the chance to work both domestically and overseas if they have the information, skills, and attitude necessary to handle the problems of the twenty-first century.

3.2. Atul Kumar (2023)⁴: Employability rates for 2011 MBA graduates in functional jobs such as finance, marketing, and human resources were less than 10 percent, they found. Employability rates were even lower (3.5% and 7.9%, respectively) for specialized occupations that required high cognitive and English abilities, such as corporate consulting and analyst positions. Through a survey of 500 students, this study examines how students from particular B-schools in Pune now perceive employability skills to address these issues.

4. AIM & OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

The aims along objectives are:

1. To look at the current system of management education in India.
2. To study the trends in management education in India
3. To study the emerging issues and future needs of management education professionals.
4. To find out the ways of current challenges and opportunities of management education.
5. To find out the outcomes of management education professionals in Indian higher educational institutions.
6. To look at the future growth and modern technology support for management education professionals.
7. To study the approval by the authorities from India for management education courses.
8. To know about the foreign collaboration and association that helps for international standardization for management education programs.
9. To find out the area of the students, success of curriculum improvement.
10. To know the future demand at the international level for management education professionals and their importance.
11. To study the management education profession facing challenges at various levels.
12. To study the opportunities of the various fields and the specialization of management education graduates.

5. FOCUS OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION:

The main focus and goal of management education is to provide people with the information, abilities, and skills they need to successfully negotiate the challenges of the

corporate environment. These include decision-making, strategic thinking, and leadership. It seeks to develop future executives who can lead teams and achieve constructive change.

1. Industrial Focus. 2. Money Focus. 3. Technovate. 5.4. Employment Focus. 5. Accreditation Focus.

6. ACADEMIC ROLES AND INSTITUTIONAL RESPONSIBILITIES:

1. The governing body's duties and responsibilities: Among other people, members of the college's governing body are recruited from the academic community, industry, and affiliated universities. The college administration receives guidance from the Governing Body. Its duties and functions include: 1. Identify the institution's academic goals and objectives and direct the institution to attain them. 2. Review and consider the suggestions made by the Local Management Committee and College Development Committee and create a plan for accomplishing the institution's objectives. 3. Keep an eye on the college's research, academic, and other relevant activities and steer them on the right path. 4. Consider and accept the staff selection committee's suggestions. 5. Consider the UGC, AICTE, Government, and University's significant communications and policy decisions, among others. 6. Support and encourage colleges to seek any necessary accreditations or certifications. 7. Assist and motivate college instructors to submit proposals and research initiatives. 8. Track faculty and student development initiatives and provide the college with the necessary direction to meet the ultimate goal. 9. Assist in launching new undergraduate and graduate programs, making decisions about ending current ones, and adjusting enrolment in any UG or PG program. 10. Make it easier to review and approve the college's annual audited income and expense statements 11. Consider any court or legal proceedings and assist the college in resolving them.

2. Functions and Duties of the Local Management Committee: 1. Making recommendations to the Governing Body about the provision of the infrastructure, human resources, and other necessities for advancing the college's goal. 2. Making it easier to oversee how the college's central library, IT infrastructure, and other learning resources are operating. 3. Encouraging the college's research culture by encouraging faculty cooperation and support. 4. Promoting cooperation with businesses and other educational institutions. 5. Establishing a supportive atmosphere for the growth of entrepreneurship. 6. Supporting and monitoring pupils' extracurricular activities. 7. Advising management to support students with medals, prizes, scholarships, stipends, and other incentives. 8. Promoting creativity and innovation among students and suggesting that management provide them with financial assistance to support this. 9. Establish committees with members drawn from the college teaching staff and outside specialists to discuss and offer advice on particular academic matters and then follow up on their recommendations after giving them careful thought. 12. Organise and carry out the college's general academic development by recommending changes to the Governing Body as needed. 13. Review the budget recommendations and approve the college's yearly budget.

3. The duties and obligations of the College Development Committee: Clause 97 of the Maharashtra Public Universities Act, 2016 (Mah. Act No. VI of 2017) established a College Development Committee (CDC). The CDC's function is as follows: 1. Create an all-encompassing strategy for the college's academic, administrative, and infrastructure development that will allow it to promote excellence in its extracurricular, co-curricular, and curricular activities. 2. Decide on the college's overall instructional programs or annual calendar. 3. Make suggestions to the management on adding more teaching and administrative positions as well as new academic courses. 4. Review and suggest ways to improve the college's self-financing courses, if any are offered. 5. Provide specific

suggestions to the management to support and enhance the college's research culture, consulting, and extension operations. 6. Provide specific suggestions to the management to support academic partnerships to improve research and teaching. 7. Provide the administration with particular suggestions to promote the use of ICT in the process of teaching and learning. 8. Provide detailed ideas for bettering instruction and appropriate training programs for college staff. 9. Create yearly financial projections (budget) and financial reports for the college or organization and submit them to management for approval. 10. Create suggestions for additional spending not included in the budget or yearly financial predictions. 11. Offer suggestions for the college's or institution's employee and student welfare initiatives. 12. Discuss and offer appropriate recommendations about the Internal Quality Assurance Committee's reports. 13. Establish appropriate admissions procedures by the statutory requirements for various programs. 14. Arrange significant yearly occasions at the college, including annual days, athletic activities, cultural events, etc. 15. Provide the administration with recommendations on how to handle the college's or institution's safety, security, and discipline issues; 16. Examine and offer suitable suggestions on inspection reports, local inquiry reports, audit reports, National Assessment and Accreditation Council reports etc. 17. Advocate for the pupils to get various accolades, medals, and prizes. 18. Compile and submit to the college and university's management the annual report on the committee's work for the year ending June 30. 19. Carry out any additional tasks and use any additional authority that may be granted by the administration and institution.

4. Roles and Duties of the Department Advisory Board: Members of the industry, alumni, students, parents, and academic professionals make up the department advisory board. Department Excellence is directed by the DAB. It serves as a catalyst to quicken the different departmental tasks necessary to achieve the desired results. It has the following duties and responsibilities: 1. To determine the curricular gap and recommend remedial majors to close or close it. 2. To encourage industry-institution interaction, industry partnerships, and industry-sponsored projects about new engineering thrust areas. 3. Redefining current PEOs, developing Program Specific Outcomes, and bringing PEOs into line with mission statements. 4. To suggest subjects outside of the curriculum, value-added training programs, and extra experiments to satisfy PEOs. 5. To provide an action plan that would help students learn the skills needed to improve quality and foster entrepreneurship. 6. To identify and recommend priority areas for conducting different activities (training courses, final year projects, and extra experiments to meet PEOs). 7. Make recommendations for bettering academic plans and standard procedures or processes to achieve PEOs.

5. The duties and obligations of the Program Assessment Committee: To keep an eye on departmental operations, the Program Assessment Committee (PAC) was established. The PAC, which is made up of the department's technical staff, faculty members, and coordinators of the programs and modules, keeps an eye on the department's operations and assesses various metrics. 1. Tracking the accomplishment of Program Outcomes (POs), Program Specific Outcomes (PSO), and Program Educational Objectives (PEOs) are among its duties and responsibilities. 2. Assessing the efficacy of the program and suggesting modifications as needed. creating regular reports for management on program operations, status, progress, and other special reports. 3. Encouraging teachers and students to participate in research activities, workshop attendance, project development, working model creation, and paper publication. 4. Getting to know students and helping them reach POs, PSOs, and PEOs. 5. Interact to Communicate with stakeholders about PO, PSO, and PEO development.

6. The principal's /Director's duties and Responsibilities: Reporting to the Institute's Executive Council and supporting them in the following duties are among the responsibilities: 1. Regulation and observation. 2. Development and Growth Function. 3. Strategic Function. 4. Leadership Function. 5. Visionary Functions. 6. Planning and executing.

7. MANAGEMENT EDUCATION SYSTEMS IN INDIA:

To equip students with managerial abilities, the Indian government and state governments have developed educational policies and taken several actions. According to the course structure of contemporary management education, individuals who have successfully finished their twelfth grade can hone their managerial skills by enrolling in a Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA) program. Universities and colleges are offering these degree programs. Anyone interested in improving their managerial skills, including decision-making, leadership, teamwork, mathematical methods, finance and banking, marketing, and human resource management, can enroll in this course from any field, including the humanities, sciences, arts, and commerce (2012)¹⁴. In a similar vein, medium and upper-level managers with a strong undergraduate degree in any discipline or a higher professional degree and a diploma in accounting, finance, and administration are advised to enroll in the two-year Master of Business Administration (MBA) program. Specialized training in accounting, finance, marketing, human resource management, general management, public sector management, insurance, and health care management is what the course is intended to offer. The goal of the M.B.A. program is to give students business-related and trade-related inputs so they may work in various organizations and overcome the difficulties that arise. The course offers the inputs required for the student's total personality development in addition to imparting information and abilities in many managerial domains.

7.1. Program Structure: Indian management education programs structures are constituted by the following statutory bodies. They are classified below.

1. National Importance Institutions like IIMs, IITs, IISc, NITS, etc.
2. University Department of Management Studies.
3. Colleges (Government or Private) affiliated university.
4. Private or Government institutes approved by the All-India Council for Technical Education (AICTE).
5. Private colleges or institutes not affiliated with any university or AICTE.
6. MBA programs are offered in India in partnership with a foreign university, where the foreign university grants the degree.

7.2. Stems of the Programme: Full-time courses for the Master of Business Administration [MBA] have long been offered. However, in recent years, a variety of MBA programs have been introduced, depending on their structure, in response to the growing need for managerial staff. On the other hand, online, remote learning, foreign, and modular MBA programs have all been used to launch part-time MBA courses. While many universities offer MBA programs in addition to other academic disciplines, some exclusively provide business degrees. MBA programs like

- a). Two-Year, Full-Time MBA & MMS
- b). One-Year, Full-Time MBA, & PGDM
- c). Part-Time MBA and PGDM
- d). Executive MBA.

Since many business schools, colleges, and MBA departments at different universities in India offer the postgraduate Master of Business Administration program, it is a highly sought-

after course for college graduates and their first choice for further education. In India, this is the most popular course for both technical and non-technical graduates. A postgraduate degree and a technical qualification are both acknowledged for an Indian MBA. The two-year MBA program is available in India. After two years, a Master of Business Administration (MBA) degree is granted upon satisfactory completion. MBA graduates may pursue further studies or begin working in the industry. There is a tonne of options for postgraduate MBA students in India and beyond. Because of the way the course is structured, students are required to take these foundational courses from various functional areas of management. Students might choose from two specializations when they are provided in functional areas later. The diploma and the Master of Business Administration (MBA) are identical.

These are the following: These include.

1. Post Graduate Program in Management (PGPM)-General Management, International Business, Infrastructure Management, Biotech Management, Marketing, Sales, IT Management, Financial Management, Human Resources Management (HR), and Family Business.
2. Post Graduate Diploma in Business Management (PGDBM).
3. Post Graduate Diploma in Business Administration (PGDBA).
4. Post Graduate Diploma in Human Resources Management (PGDHRM).
5. Post Graduate Diploma in Biotechnology Management (PGD Biotech), with a focus on IT Management.
6. Post Graduate Diploma in Finance Management (PGDFM), and
7. The Executive MBA (e-MBA) Program.

7.3. Specialization offered in Indian Management Schools: India's business management studies institutes provide a range of specializations. About 19% of business and management studies colleges in the nation provide finance, sales, and marketing as their most popular specializations. This graph illustrates the proportion of universities that provide students with certain specializations.

Marketing Management. • Operations Management & System. • Finance Management. • OB & HR • General Management (Economics, Corporate Ethics, Entrepreneurship, Strategy, Business Law, etc.) • International Business • Corporate Governance.

Fig. 1. Top Business & Management studies specializations offered by Colleges in India

Diploma in Hospitality Management. Bachelor's degree in culinary management, MBA/PGDM (Hospitality Management). MBA/PGDM (Tourism and Travel Management).

7. 4. Future of Course Development Programmes with AI Technology: Businesses throughout the world are changing because of AI and data science. As the rate of change quickens, the value addition must also quicken. The Data Science and AI Program was introduced by IIM Kozhikode to assist you in scaling data science, reaping benefits, and obtaining a career upgrade. Make the most of the many career options in this sector by becoming proficient in practical and useful data science, machine learning, and artificial intelligence tools and techniques. Acquire cutting-edge abilities and information to address frequent problems, record ongoing insights, and make more intelligent decisions. Utilise generative AI to generate value and open the next growth frontier to optimize earnings and return on investment.

Examples:

1. IIM Kozhikode - Professional Certificate Programme in Data Science and Artificial Intelligence for Managers.
2. IIM Bangalore-Certificate Programme in Artificial Intelligence for Managers.
3. IIM Mumbai – Generative AI for Business Decisions.
4. AIMA – Certificate Course on Digital Business Management.
5. IIBM- Online Courses on AI for Business Professions.

7.5. Career Choices in Business Management: You will be able to obtain employment in a variety of industries with a business management degree, including marketing, telecom, IT, finance, and real estate. Your decision on the type of education method and management degree will be aided by your knowledge of the various occupations. The top ten business management career opportunities are: Manager of social media. Manager of marketing. Manager of human resources. Manager of sales. Manager of operations. Business analyst. Chief Executive Leader. Manager of accounting. Manager of finance, and data analyst (2024)¹⁷.

8. CHALLENGES OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION:

There are a variety of difficulties, some distinct and the majority interconnected. These can be broadly categorized as knowledge and abilities associated with a broad behavioral influence. This results from a combination of enrolling low-quality kids in underequipped institutions and a lack of qualified faculty. Because teaching is underappreciated and under-rewarded in India, it cannot draw in top talent. Some basic improvements are required to remedy this. The gap between academia and industry is yet another crucial problem. Program curriculum is frequently out of current and out of step with the quickly changing needs of the industry. As a result, when they start working, business graduates from many institutions are not “battle-ready”! As a result, the “quantity versus quality” dilemma is currently pressing us. Program standards for management vary greatly throughout schools. This particularly affects lower-tier schools that lack qualified teachers and the necessary facilities. Large recruiters choose elite schools like the more established IIMs and ISB since they are primarily concerned in hiring the best personnel. As a result, the current system produces a “dual citizenry” of corporate managers, which breeds dissatisfaction. In addition to these significant behavioral and structural issues, there is difficulty in preserving the caliber of program delivery. In addition to legal limitations, other

issues that still hinder the growth of this industry include management institutions' outdated teaching methods and the slow pace of technology use (2021)¹³.

8.1. Time investment: Many MBA programs demand full-time enrolment, and they usually require a substantial time commitment. For those who already have a job or other personal obligations, this could be difficult.

8.2. Cost of Education: For over ten years, government support for higher education, particularly management education, has been steadily declining. Due to the government's decision to stop funding higher education, private institutions are now able to assume responsibility for educating everyone. Additionally, the self-financing and self-sustaining institution model has been applied at government-aided institutions. The expense of schooling has increased significantly because of all these advances. Even though education loans have been made easier to access to support higher education and management training, banks' terms and conditions regarding guarantees and family income limit the ability of talented individuals from low-income families to pursue higher education and management training.

8.3. Global Level Competition: The nature of the management education system is dynamic. Its response to sociological, technical, and economic shifts in the local and global context is fraught with difficulties. The importance of management education and its significance in a country's social and economic growth is not as much of a topic anymore. Most people agree that management education is a crucial component of the whole system of education and training. As a WTO member, India must open its market to trade in services, including education, but it lacks a clear plan to improve its educational system so it can compete with the global giants. Therefore, the higher management education system urgently needs to be freed from needless restrictions and given an academic and administrative framework that is transparent, egalitarian, and responsible (2021)¹¹.

9. OPPORTUNITIES AND CHANCES FOR MANAGEMENT EDUCATION PROGRAM:

There are several chances to get better at the Management Institute, specifically.

1. Developing managerial skills and shaping leadership potential through the implementation of suitable practical training and awareness programs on creativity and personality development considering and embracing marketing opportunities.

2. Increasing managerial behavior and attitudes to improve communication and conflict resolution abilities.

3. Improving the standard of the business education curriculum, which gives students global information to help them make decisions.

4. Changing the admissions and curriculum development processes to make the institute stronger

5. Making the summer placement program possible to enhance students' understanding of the industries' managerial aspects.

6. The faculty induction program offers a chance to acquire new approaches and strategies for managing the institute's students and resources.

7. Opening campuses abroad gives academics and students the chance to experience other cultures and work environments (2019)⁵.

10. DATA ANALYSIS:

10.1. Sex-wise employability of management graduates: Only 50.9% of women were deemed employable in 2024, compared to 51.8% of men. Based on their labor force

participation rate, only about 37% of India's employable women are either working or looking for work, while their employability¹⁶ within the country's workforce is just 50.9%.

Fig.2. Sex-wise employability of management graduates. Source: India skill report. Wheebos.

10.2. Management graduates’ employability across India from 2015-2024: In 2024, the employment rate for Indian MBA graduates was 71%, up from 47% in 2021, according to Mirrorty and statista.com. As a result, MBA graduates are the most employable group in India, followed by 64.7% of B.E./B.Tech graduates. The Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS), conducted by the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI), is the main source of information on employment and unemployment in India. The PLFS has been carried out every year since 2017–18.

Fig.3. Employability from 2015-2024 Sources: Statistica¹⁵

10.3. Education-wise employability: The most employable cohort in 2024 was those with management degrees (71.2%), followed by those with BE/B. Tech degrees (94.7%).

Fig.4. Education-wise Employability in 2024. Sources: India Skill Report, Wheebox and Mirrority¹⁶

10.4. Key Economic Events Affecting India’s Unemployment Rate: Because of several significant economic events, India’s unemployment rate has changed over time (2024)¹⁶.

1. International Financial Crisis (2008-2009).
2. The demonetization of 2016.
3. 2020’s COVID-19 pandemic.
4. The Impact of Inflation.

Employment outcomes by years after graduation:

Fig.5. Employment outcomes by years after graduation: Sources: Burning Glass Institute Database 2022²¹.

10.5. Growth of AICTE Approved Management Institutes in India:

Growth of AICTE approved Management & Technical Institutions in the last ten years¹.

Year	No. of Institutes	No of Intakes	%
2023-24	3280	3 38 476	1.03
2022-23	3133	4 20 236	1.34
2021-22	3107	4 03 202	1.30
2020-21	3084	3 85 541	1.25
2019-20	3036	3 71 850	1.22
2018-19	3084	3 72 399	1.21
2017-18	3233	3 93 043	1.22

2016-17	3334	4 11 826	1.24
2015-16	3449	4 31 728	1.25
2014-15	3586	4 54 917	1.27

Tab.1. AICTE Approved Management Education Institutes. Sources: AICTE^{25&26}

The table reflects the management course and students' interest in choosing their career for their future in the postgraduate course. As per the AICTE norms, they must fulfill the mandatory degree requirements with the completion of the entrance test examination and score good marks, based on the percentage of their marks they are allowed to take a seat from the top institute to low-level institutions. In the table, the student's intakes are based on the number of institutions from 2014 to 2024 academic years. 2014-15 to 2020-21 The student ratio decreases every year because they have not shown their interest in management education. After 2021-22 based on the IT industries opportunities students have shown their interest in selecting the management program and the intakes have been increased. From these data, the research confirms that the opportunities have everyone shown an interest in selecting career opportunities at the national and global levels to get jobs in various fields.

Fig.6. AICTE Approved Management Education Institutes. Sources: AICTE²⁵

2024 AICTE-approved management course uplifted in Indian Institutes with seating capabilities.

Sl.No.	Region	Statues	No. of Institutions	No. of Seats
1	South	Tamil Nadu	188	14400
		Pondicherry	002	60
2	Gujarat	Gujrat	078	6100
		Madhya Pradesh	079	7235
		Chhatisgarh	008	900
3	East	Orissa	038	3759
		Assam	008	360
		West Bengal	034	2365
		Manipur	001	30
		Sikkim	001	60
		Tripur	001	60
		Meghalaya	000	-
		Mizoram	000	-
		Jharkhand	004	270

4	North	Uttar Pradesh	202	14828
		Uttarkhand	029	1710
		Bihar	013	955
5	West	Maharashtra	203	18905
		Goa	001	-
6	Karnataka	Karnataka	117	9470
		Kerala	033	2560
7	South Centre	Andhra Pradesh	310	25840
8	North West	Delhi	010	1090
		Haryana	080	5525
		Rajasthan	077	5780
		Jammu & Kashmir	009	540
		Himachal Pradesh	009	540
		Chandigarh	001	60
		Punjab	072	5520
		Grand Total	1 608	1, 28, 922

Tab.2. AICTE Approved Management Education Institutes. Sources: AICTE¹

10.6. Outputs:

Types of Degree-Granting Institutions:

S.No	Universities	Total
1	Central Universities	056
2	State Universities	487
3	Deemed to be Universities	137
4	State Private Universities	491
	Total	1171

Tab.3. Degree Granting Institutions. Sources: UGC¹⁹

Autonomous Colleges: As of 2023-24, there are more than 5,600 colleges in India that offer management education, including PGDM or MBA. PGDM is a diploma offered by autonomous institutions that are approved by the AICTE. It is considered equivalent to an MBA, and

S.No	Autonomous Colleges	Management	Others	Total
1	Registered	5600	4378	1222

recruiters may consider either when hiring candidates.

Tab.4. Degree Granting Institutions. Sources: UGC¹⁹ MoE¹³

Standalone Institutes: As of 2020, there were 11,296 standalone institutions in India. Standalone institutions are different from universities and colleges, which are affiliated or recognized with universities. Standalone institutions offer diploma certification instead of degrees.

S.No	Standalone Institutes	Management	Other	Total
1	Registered	5713	5583	11 296

Tab5. Standalone Institutions. Sources: MoE¹³

As of 2010–11, 5,713 standalone institutions uploaded data on the AISHE portal. India has more than 5,600 colleges that offer management education, including PGDM and MBA. The main difference between PGDM and MBA is the type of educational institution and its ability to change the curriculum.

Institutions of National Importance (Under the Ministry of Govt. of India):

S.No	Institutes of National Importance	Management	Other	Total
1	Registered			165

Tab.6. *Institutions of National Importance. Sources: MoE¹³*

10.7. Workforce Employability: Employability is a collection of accomplishments, including knowledge, abilities, and character traits, that increase graduates' chances of landing a job and succeeding in their chosen fields, which benefits the workforce, the economy, the community, and oneself.

Fig.7. *Workforce employability. Source: India skill report. Wheebos.*

Therefore, being employable involves more than just landing a job; it also involves having a wider range of abilities and qualities that will help a graduate succeed in their career. India Skills Report: 52.3% of recent graduates were deemed employable by the industry in 2024, a 2% rise from the previous year. Only 63.6% of the 22–25 age group's most employable skill pool is employable⁴.

10.8. All-India Employment Rates: The all-India annual unemployment rate increased from 7.6% in 2022–2023 to 8.2% in 2023–2024. When someone actively looks for a job but is unsuccessful, they are considered unemployed. In the Indian economy, underemployment and unemployment have long been issues. Founded in 1976 as a premier business information organization, the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE)²² primarily serves as an independent think tank. The Consumer Pyramids Household Survey equipment is used by CMIE to generate the unemployment rates. When using the unemployment rate, it only includes unemployed people, wanting to work, and actively seeking employment because it is more pertinent and produces a lower unemployment rate. In July 2024, the unemployment rate in all of India fell from 9.2% to 7.9%.

Fig.8. All India Rural and Urban Unemployment. Source: CMIE²²

Fig.9. Unemployment Across India States. Sources: StudyIQ²²

Kerala: Kerala had one of the highest youth unemployment rates in the 15-29 age group at 29.9%, with an alarming 47.1% among females and 19.3% among males by PLFS²⁴ 2023-24 Data²².

Madhya Pradesh: Recorded the lowest youth unemployment rate at 3.2%, followed closely by Gujarat²⁴.

Union Territories: Lakshadweep reported the highest youth unemployment rate at 36.2%, with female joblessness soaring to 79.7%. Andaman & Nicobar Islands also had a high rate of 33.6%.

Urban vs. Rural: In urban areas, the youth unemployment rate stood at 14.7%, significantly higher than the rural rate of 8.5%. Female unemployment was notably higher in urban areas at 20.1%, compared to 8.2% in rural areas²⁴.

10.9. Projected Unemployment Rates in India: Since India's economy has grown at the quickest rate in the globe since the COVID-19 pandemic, the country's job market is changing. The nation's youthful population, with a median age of 28.4 years, is crucial to promoting economic growth. Underpinned by robust private consumption and public investment, India's GDP growth rate of 7.8% might help it reach its goal of being a US\$5 trillion economy by 2026–2027.

Fig.10. Projected unemployment rates in India reach US\$ 5.09 trillion. Sources: IMF²², ILO^{9&7}

11. DISCUSSION:

In June 2024, the unemployment rate increased to 9.2%. According to the Consumer Pyramids Household Survey conducted by CMIE, the unemployment rate in India increased significantly from 7% in May 2024 to 9.2% in June 2024. Both in rural and urban areas of India, the jobless rate rose. The rural unemployment rate increased from 6.3% in May to 9.3% in June. The urban unemployment rate increased from 8.6% to 8.9%. In June, the unemployment rate went up while the labour participation rate (LPR) went up and the employment rate went down. In June, LPR increased to 41.4% in India from 40.8% in the previous month. The percentage of people in the working-age population who are employed, or the employment rate, decreased from 38% to 37.2 percent in June 2024²².

Unemployment: India's service sector has a bright future because it has the highest employment elasticity to economic expansion. Ten service sector opportunity subsectors with the most potential for expansion and job creation for the Indian economy by 2030 are highlighted in this paper. These opportunity sectors include global capability centers; renewable energy; e-commerce; MSMEs; the startup ecosystem; digital services (also known as the content economy or the Fourth Industrial Revolution, or 4IR); financial services (banking and insurance); health services; hospitality services; consumer retail services; and global capability centers. By 2030, these industries might collectively provide over 100 million new employments.

12. SUGGESTIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS:

12.1. Recommendations:

1. To identify employability gaps, policymakers should work with employers in the commercial sector, educational institutions, and civil society organizations. In order to improve the employability and productivity of young people, curriculum modifications and program designs should be in line with changing labour market demands.

2. Diversifying skill sets is essential, as is fostering cutting-edge technology capabilities and work skills that are resistant to technological advancements. For ongoing human capital development, bridge courses and formal mentorship programs are necessary.

3. Natural changes in employment sectors must be supported by governments and other important players in all economic sectors, with a focus on industries with high employment elasticity including travel, hospitality, finance, and healthcare. To utilize the

excess labour that is liberated as a result of technical breakthroughs in Indian manufacturing, growth in these service industries must be given priority.

4. In order to foster innovation, encourage youth involvement, and support the growth of the startup ecosystem, it is imperative to provide an atmosphere that is conducive to entrepreneurship. By supporting small businesses and creating gender-sensitive work conditions, this can also increase the number of women in the workforce.

5. Public-private cooperation is essential for building trained, semi-skilled, and job-ready workforces as well as for starting or expanding R&D divisions in companies to spur innovation and generate job opportunities.

6. To boost employment, public policies and programs like PM Vishwakarma Yojana, Startup India, Digital India, Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY), and Production Linked Incentive (PLI) Schemes must be used. To draw in investments and generate employment in labour-intensive export industries, the government must negotiate advantageous trade agreements.

12.2.Suggestions:

The entire framework, subject matter, goal, and pattern of management education must be reexamine considering this. The national government and statutory bodies make alternative systems and reexamine the regulatory system for domestic, national, and international growth, and it will help the economic growth from the house to the global level and help to entire economic policy⁸.

A. Issues with Management Education Today:

Issue 1: Inappropriate Admission Requirements: Most B schools currently use a selection method that emphasizes testing students' written English and mathematical ability. The qualitative method of evaluating the competencies—*influencing, relationship management, interpersonal skills, problem-solving, decision-making, personal organization, and time management*—that are critical to effective leadership and management is absent from their testing. As a result, occasionally the Caliber of candidates who make the shortlist falls short of what the business requires.

Issue 2: Insufficient Practitioners as Faculty: More academicians than practitioners are employed as faculty at many business schools. The knowledge that faculty members share becomes theoretical or taken from international B schools, which may not apply to the Indian environment, because academicians lack firsthand experience of crucial business circumstances. Additionally, B schools struggle to find qualified instructors with doctorates or significant work experience.

Issue 3: Insufficient Use of a Practical Approach: The limitations of the theories taught in business schools, the degree of difficulty and complexity of putting them into practice, the related abilities and dispositions needed for careful, efficient application, and the critical lenses and judgment required to accurately assess a given context and reach the right conclusions are all things that are frequently overlooked.

Issue 4: B Schools as Placement Organizations: Most business schools position themselves as placement organizations. The emphasis is now on "the want of placements" rather than "the need of learning." The difficulty lies in changing the environment from one that emphasizes job hunting to one that encourages study.

Issue 5: Students from rural and economically disadvantaged backgrounds are not given enough attention. The majority of B Schools charge excessive tuition, making management education unaffordable for intelligent but economically disadvantaged students. Students from rural backgrounds struggle in the competitive field of management education because they frequently lack the personality development component.

Issue 6: Not enough attention is paid to rural management/ Require Inadequacy

Focus:

India is a nation that relies heavily on agriculture. Agriculture accounts for around 14.6% of the Indian economy's GDP. With it, 58.2% of the workforce is employed. The Institute of Rural Management Anand (IRMA) is one of the few management institutes in our country that teaches rural management as one of the key domains, along with marketing, finance, operations, and human resources⁸.

B. Needs of Management Education:

1. Unfulfilled Demands for Management Education: Many unmet demands have been found when examining the issues with MBA programs in India. MBA programs have the chance to develop and adapt to each requirement. A better economy and learning curve would result from meeting these needs.

2. Pay Attention to Leadership: India's GDP is expected to grow by 8.8% in 2009–2010, up from 6.8% in 2008–2009. It is one of the few countries that managed to withstand the effects of the 2007 financial crisis and continues to grow rapidly. In the ten years after 1997, the economy has grown at an average rate of almost 7%. The world views India as a vast reservoir of potential and as a superpower on the rise. India is dealing with several problems despite its accomplishments, including poverty, unemployment, illiteracy, Maoist attacks, terrorism, corruption, Indo-Pakistani tensions, regional riots, and many more. Mahatma Gandhi, Sardar Ballabh Bhai Patel, and Bhagat Singh were among the great leaders of India, as evidenced by their leadership in the face of instability and upheaval. This is the highest level of leadership in any field that India has seen in a long time.

In the current situation, no one is prepared to assertively and clearly express a viewpoint on India to unite the nation and make the sacrifices required to create a new India. India is experiencing a severe leadership crisis, which arises when societies and organizations overemphasize short-term and limited thinking. For India to overcome its leadership crisis and achieve greater economic growth, it must prioritize people, their potential, and their empowerment. India's destiny can be greatly improved and its leadership dilemma resolved with the help of B schools. As Indian citizens, B-school students should learn to assume their duties and make thoughtful decisions⁸.

3. Creation of a Worldwide Viewpoint: With its growing economy, India is expected to have several job opportunities to represent the country internationally. As one of the fastest-growing economies, India needs to learn how to adjust to a wide range of institutional, social, and commercial norms, as well as local, national, and international laws. This calls for a new set of abilities to react correctly to the strange and frequently unclear words, gestures, and behaviors of individuals from other nations and cultures. Therefore, the B Schools should be fostering the next generation so that they can learn how to conduct business in various nations and cultures.

4. Encouragement of Affordable Innovation: With a population of 1.5 billion and a low level of economic buying power, India requires the latest technologies at reasonable costs. Given that agriculture dominates the economy, farmers require modern technologies to increase output. As per the NSS 61st round's 2004-2005 Uniform Recall Period (URP) consumption distribution data, 27.5% of India's population is classified as "Below Poverty Line (BPL)". The B Schools ought to make their pupils more aware of these demands and encourage them to develop more creative solutions and ideas to raise people's standards of living.

5. Promotion of Entrepreneurial Capabilities: Instead of entering the corporate world and managing someone else's firm, Indian B schools ought to encourage their

graduates to launch their businesses. Thus, the economy would be strengthened, and new job opportunities would be created for the unemployed.

6. Pay attention to Focus ethics and values: The Corruption Perception Index has placed India at number 84 out of 180 nations in terms of corruption. A bribe was previously paid to complete incorrect tasks. However, bribery is now compensated for the timely completion of tasks. To help graduates develop fundamental ethical principles, including justice, respect, accountability, compassion, and citizenship, B schools can assist in creating character education programs. The idea of teaching moral principles in schools is widely supported. According to a recent poll, 84% of parents whose children were in B Schools desired that moral behavior training be taught in B Schools, incorporating democratic methods in the formation of class norms. B schools have the potential to become more compassionate places, lessen disruptive student conduct, and produce graduates who are capable of being responsible members of society.

7. Importance of Design and Critical Thinking: Management education must equip students to meet the challenges of today's evolving world, which include India's rapidly expanding economy, the country's booming domestic markets and international opportunities, and the resulting rise in interest in India by both foreign and Indian businesses abroad.

Critical and creative thinking, as well as the ability to approach problems from multiple angles and integrate different techniques to come up with novel solutions, are all skills that students in B-School should learn.

8. Soft skill development: As the corporate world continues to grow and become multinational corporations, both clients and employees require good interpersonal skills to effectively comprehend and interact with one another. Time management, effective bargaining, and a well-groomed demeanour are all examples of interpersonal skills. Both domestic and multinational corporations are starting to consider these talents when choosing new hires. When it comes to the significance of soft skills for an MBA graduate, these abilities are now required for management-level hiring. As a result, soft skills must be included in the B Schools' course curriculum as a required subject. For managers, these soft skills are becoming more and more crucial. In every aspect of management, including marketing, banking, and human resources, having outstanding people skills is crucial for both success and efficient operation.

9. Social Responsibility and Sensitivity: Values are touched wherever we encounter the future. The values center on passion, wanting to make a difference, and wanting to give back. In the immoral and careless world of today, people must be passionate about social justice and change to advance our economy. All organizations must be more than just IT companies, carbon core companies, or iron ore companies. B Schools should be devoted to working in a way that makes people feel happy to be affiliated with this wonderful nation at night, in addition to helping graduates to become social, responsible, caring, committed, and enthusiastic to provide a good return on other people's capital.

10. Encouraging Political Participation: India is a democratic nation. Since independence, the manner politics is conducted has undergone significant change. The impact of corruption has been negative, and unethical behavior has escalated. Individuals are entering politics to further their agendas at the expense of the nation's interests. Frequently, justice is postponed and ignored. People no longer have faith in politicians as a result. When it comes to politics, everyone complains, but nobody wants to get involved that way. B schools have a vital role to play in motivating students to get involved in politics for the sake of the nation and to change things.

11. Motivated Leadership: A Suggested Structure for Enhancing Management Education: In the modern world, people are growing increasingly business-oriented and, despite this, losing interest in the growth of the Indian economy. The candidate's goal after graduating from the B School is to pursue an unethical path to financial gain. According to the findings, B schools must reevaluate the facts, frameworks, and theories they teach to produce successful leaders and entrepreneurs. They must also rebalance the curriculum to give greater emphasis to developing the competencies, skills, and abilities that are fundamental to human nature as well as the values, attitudes, and beliefs that shape managers' professional identities. Keeping in mind the necessity of the same, we suggest a paradigm that emphasizes "Inspired Leadership." A person who is ethical at heart, observant of his actions, considerate of others, believes in diversity, and employs a sustainable method to accomplish his objectives is an inspired leader. The following is an inspired leadership model.

12. "Mindfulness" and "self-awareness" are central: We need them to become more aware of the decisions we make. If only we would use our consciousness to pay attention, we would realize the effects of our lifestyle choices. This would increase our "compassion" for the less fortunate and those who are suffering. We'd be forced to consider how we use the planet's resources and discover why the green economy and global warming are such pressing challenges for every one of us. As a result, our organization would be able to draw in individuals who are truly diverse and who bring a variety of creative, emotional, and spiritual intelligence. People like them would make us reevaluate our presumptions and advance our awareness and evolution. The distinction between the "right" things to do and our basic "rights" to think and act is what ethics is. Thus, these are the five pillars of "inspired leadership": sustainability, diversity, ethics, mindfulness, and compassion.

Be mindfulness: Being aware means being present in the moment. We need self-awareness and mindfulness to become more mindful of the decisions we make. Our "souls" oversee the five senses and the perceptual process, as well as the way our bodies are used in conjunction with our minds and intellects.

13. Having compassion: Having empathy for other people causes us to consider the effects of our actions on them. It entails realizing the truth about our integrity as well as the truth and integrity of all parties involved in the business, organization, or civil service. Even in situations where they lack sufficient resources for themselves, inspired leaders cultivate empathy for others. Management schools ought to install in their students the idea that the knowledge and research they generate benefit society. Students should be taught to care more profoundly about their responsibilities, to be passionate about what they do, and to have empathy for the people they work for.

14. Sustainability: Since India is currently experiencing growth, it is crucial to ensure that the development is sustainable. The main goal of this is to prevent any significant changes in our nation's economic trajectory in the future. For our nation to thrive sustainably, businesses must take two important steps: implementing a triple-bottom-line idea and encouraging innovation within their organizations. For the organization to be considered creative, its culture must shift, making the entire system flexible enough to accommodate new practices. It should be ingrained in the organization's culture for its employees to innovate. For example, as everyone knows, our nation is service-based, and businesses that rely on services for their revenue are dependent on wealthy countries. The economic curve will therefore change if they cease outsourcing. Therefore, the time for our nation to take action to establish sustainable enterprises has come. Sustainability is no longer an option; it is

now essential to the survival of businesses. Instead of being a cost center, this should be viewed as a revenue-generating project. Future company executives should be able to design their company to have the three sustainability dimensions of innovation, people, and planet to generate profits.

15. Diversity: Every individual has different knowledge, abilities, and dispositions. Students in management schools must be encouraged to fully utilize their individuality, value the qualities and distinctiveness of others, comprehend their mission, and connect it to their work. It also discusses the idea of "multiple intelligences." People are born with and develop many forms of multiple intelligences, including musical, spatial, verbal, intrapersonal, and spiritual intelligence. The following changes should be implemented to raise students' awareness of diversity: *1. Leadership Series:* This initiative allows leaders from a variety of fields, including government, business, environmental advocacy, freedom fighters, and entrepreneurship, to visit colleges and engage with students. Students would gain a broad view and learn about the many sectors as a result. *2. Program for Global Leadership:* Global leaders from around the globe may be invited to the college as part of this program to engage with students. Students will get the chance to learn about international challenges affecting many nations and how these leaders are addressing them. *3. Coaching and Mentoring:* Each student in this program may be paired with an industry mentor. To help students learn as much as possible in their chosen sector, these mentors can be appointed based on the student's career choices. Students can receive guidance and assistance from mentors in making wise decisions. Students can benefit from mentors' real-world experiences⁸.

CONCLUSION:

Indian business schools' ability to anticipate change and adjust to the changing demands will determine how successful they are. The winners will be those who work with other schools, create novel programs, and proactively evaluate the shifting demands of the sector. This move will be welcomed and beneficial to students, recruiters, institutions, and most importantly, our country! Both opportunities and difficulties are presented by India's employment forecast for 2030; to take advantage of these chances, pertinent stakeholders—including the government, the commercial sector, civil society, and individuals—must act in concert and strategically. The goal is to realize India's vision of an economy that is skilled, innovative, self-sufficient, and empowered by digital technology. Therefore, all colleges address the tragedies, create new job opportunities through their respective suppliers, and offer quality placement services before graduation.

India's future development depends heavily on management education. Recruiters are trying to hire an increasing number of non-MBA grads as time goes on. The system no longer contains the value addition that it once did. An organization that once had a 50/50 split between MBA and non-MBA grads is now leaning more toward the latter. The value addition that high school graduates once brought to the table is no longer present. Graduates are less concerned with learning and more with making money. The desire to comprehend how various processes are integrated is waning daily. The impoverished segment of society receives the least attention from graduates, who are growing more self-centered²⁴. Without considering the consequences, society is preoccupied with using unethical tactics to achieve success. Therefore, the B Schools must produce leaders who are not limited to industry, who can learn to integrate all management functions and avoid becoming narrow specialists, who are interested in improving society rather than just making money for themselves, who are humane and not authoritarian in style, who are open to learning and applying new skills and

techniques, who are willing to work with people from different cultures, and who wish to improve the lives of the less fortunate and impoverished.

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